

A crowdsourced Ecosystem to fight Childhood Cancer

We are designing an interoperable **EU framework** for research on **Artificial Intelligence (AI)**, active **collaboration** and **knowledge exchange** on **Pediatric Cancer**

Why Childhood Cancer?

The facts

Many paediatric cancers have a genetically distinct component from their adult counterparts, highlighting a need for **childhood-specific genomic studies, datasets** and **therapeutic strategies**

Specificity is the mark

Early detection is key

Young survivors deserve better

Our tools

AI medical imaging

Natural Language Processing

Deep Neural Networks

A multidisciplinary roadmap to fight Childhood Cancer

A multi-perspective State-of-the-Art, complemented by a **roadmap** and **guidelines** on the **mechanisms and tools** to implement the ecosystem

Bringing together clinicians, young cancer patients and AI experts

We seek to connect **key European stakeholders** in Childhood Cancer by means of **eXplainable AI** to facilitate their interaction and cooperation

A single access point to boost knowledge exchange and collaboration

Our ambition

Our one-stop portal will host and curate a EU-wide knowledge base for Childhood Cancer, providing insights on the disease and liaising future opportunities for collaboration

Fostering **Open Innovation**

Enabling **interoperability**

Top **AI performance and quality**

A **sound data strategy**

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